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"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

Research in progress

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The mutual reinforcement of scientific and technological knowledge: a micro-level analysis

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Research in Progress

The advances in science and the progress in the development of technologies mutually inspire and reinforce each other, but the quantitative studies are mostly limited to the effects that scientific research exerts on technological progress, while the opposite direction is empirically under-researched. The reason for that is the asymmetric nature of citations: patents cite articles much more often than the other way round. In this paper we attempt to overcome this problem by linking publications to patents using machine-learning software that had been trained on patents' abstracts.

It has long been recognized that useful knowledge can be categorized according to its direct applicability in practical contexts. Mokyr (2002) differentiates between “propositional knowledge” and “prescriptive knowledge”. He argues that the two types of knowledge are mutually reinforcing. Propositional knowledge constitutes the epistemic base that makes it possible to develop further, to adapt, and to legitimize the techniques forming prescriptive knowledge. However, there are also positive feedbacks from prescriptive knowledge to propositional knowledge. Improved techniques strengthen the confidence in propositional knowledge underlying them, which leads to further work in the respective fields.

Serendipitous discoveries in technology can launch whole new streams of scientific research. And technological progress in research equipment enhances scientific productivity.

Recent years saw a number of excellent studies on how scientific progress contributes to the technology development. This approach is consistent with formal modelling in neoclassical economics that assumes a “technology production function”, and with the experience of the science-based technological progress, characteristic for the postwar economy. In terms of methodology, most of these works analyze citations to scientific articles in patent applications. Examples include Watzinger and Schnitzer (2019), who use the metrics developed by Ahmadpoor and Jones (2017), Poege et al. (2019), and Fleming et al. (2019). However the effect of technology on science has not been investigated to a similar extent, probably because relatively few papers cite patents, so the citation link is not particularly useful.

The contribution of this paper is that we attempt to look at mutual reinforcement of science and technology, by linking publications to patents using machine-learning software that had been trained on patents' abstracts. Text analysis has been increasingly applied in the empirical research of science and education (see Arora et al., 2022; Biasi and Ma, 2022), but so far this has been done in slightly different contexts. Here it is used to create datasets of technology-level dataset amounts of patents and papers, for almost all countries in the 1990- 2016.

We utilize data on more than 5 million patents and 1.73 million scientific articles from Web of Science while focusing on 109 “technologies” that we identify with fastest-growing IPC subclasses. Articles were classified to IPC subclasses through a combination of machine-learning and expert approach. The procedure consisted of two steps. First, a classifier was developed using the PyTorch library. The classifier was trained to recognize the 109 IPC subclasses: to that end about 0.5% of the total population of English language patent applications from 1990-2016 available in the PATSTAT Global database were used (about 15M records). In the next step, the classifier (trained on patents) was applied to ca. 1.9 million scientific articles i.e. a “transfer-learning” procedure was attempted. One article could be classified to several IPC subclasses. However, the results of this classification were put under additional scrutiny using the division of Web of Science articles into scientific categories. The procedure involved an external expert – a junior patent attorney, who defined a set of WoS categories that in her view could be expected to contribute to the knowledge applied each IPC subclass. For a scientific article to be assigned to a given IPC subclass it had to be classified so by the classifier and it had to meet the criteria defined by the expert.

The articles were also classified according to their geographical location and sector affiliation. The former classification utilized the address information, while the latter was based on text analysis. Only two sectors were distinguished: academic and non-academic.

The outcome of this exercise is a dataset whose elements are indexed by a quadruple (j, c, s, t). For example, we aggregate patents into categories such as y_{jcst} which is the number of priority applications in technology j , country c , sector s , and year t . The total number of records in our final dataset is 1,280,860, but the total number of records with a positive number of patents is 127,393.

In the empirical analysis, we look at the mutual effects of advances in science and in technology, in terms of the extensive and intensive margins. As for the former, we investigate if the incidence of a patent application (journal article) characterized by (j, c, s, t) increases the probability of the incidence of the article (patent application) in (j, c, s, t) . To analyze the intensive margin we look at the relationship between y_{jcst} and x_{jcst} , the respective amount of journal articles. To address the endogeneity problem, we instrument the respective variables by the values for substantially less advanced countries (alternative instruments, based on bibliometric distance are being developed). Additional country- and industry level covariates are utilized. We apply linear model and Tobit model with endogenous regressors.

The results indicate a certain asymmetry of effects, with the effects of science on technology consistently stronger than the opposite effect. For instance, for the OECD countries the incidence of a publication increases the probability of an occurrence of a patent by 7.6 pp while the opposite effect is 2.7 pp. However both estimates are statistically significant. We find similar differences in the analysis of the intensive margin.

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